

Policy Cloud
Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This deliverable compiles the aspects related to the Development of the pilot cases of the PolicyCloud project

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
ITA	Instituto tecnológico de Aragón
LEAs	Law Enforcement and Society
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LON	London Borough of Camden
MAG	Maggioli
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
SC	Scenario
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SOF	Municipality of Sofia
UC	Use Case

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to make an initial description of the pilots and scenarios defined in PolicyCloud proposal. Furthermore, the document collects the different scenarios of each pilot case, the fundamental actors (stakeholders) of the same, as well as the main KPIs from 3 political, technical and business points of view.

This information has been defined taking into account the information coming from the pilots, as well as the previous experience of the partners. Therefore, this document is the basis to define the main features to be provided by Policycloud and is used for the pilots' implementation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the following deliverable, we will review the 4 use cases of the Policycloud project, focusing on their different scenarios, the KPIs from three points of view in addition to the visualization requirements.

The objective of this deliverable is to know the main indicators to be achieved within the scenarios reflected by the partners. One of the main objectives of the deliverables is to know the visualization requirements of the future tools, an essential part for the development and correct use of the same.

2 MAGGIOLI Use Case 1

2.1 Description

2.1.1 General Description

Use Case 1: Participatory policies against Radicalization

This use case will develop a collaborative data-driven analysis for the validation of existing policies against radicalization based on a participatory review of data coming from social media (e.g. Twitter, Reddit, RSS feeds) and open datasets (e.g. Global Terrorism Database (GTD) and RAND Database of Worldwide Terrorism). In addition, it will provide useful insights and valuable information to policy makers at any level (local/regional, national and EU level) to update current policies and/or create new ones, while at the same time allow them to interact with other relevant stakeholders (i.e. LEAs, social services, schools, civil society) during the creation and modelling of new policies and specific countermeasures, ranging from early detection methodologies to techniques and policies for the monitoring and management of domestic radicalization.

2.1.2 Main Objectives

- The use case objectives are through PolicyCLOUD big data streaming and real-time big data platform to improve operational efficiency, transparency, and decision making. The PolicyCLOUD visualisation technologies will enable policy makers to identify issues, trends, and policy effects and interactions. The PolicyCLOUD analytics technologies will enable to discover insights and find meaningful explanations about the effects of policies.

2.1.3 Use cases scenarios

Name	Description	Goals
Scenario A	<p>Visualize a heatmap that shows the frequency of occurrence of radicalization incidents in the geographic proximity of a region.</p> <p>Data coming from the GTD will be used.</p> <p>The Policy Maker can select the area of his/her interest and consult the different incidents that have taken place in a given period.</p>	<p>Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.</p>

Name	Description	Goals
Scenario B	<p>Visualize a bar chart that shows the main actors (individuals or groups) involved in radicalization efforts.</p> <p>Data coming from the GTD will be used.</p> <p>The Policy Maker can select the individuals/groups active in the area of his/her interest and consult the different incidents that are linked to each of them.</p>	<p>To identify main actors (individuals or groups) involved in violent incidents or propaganda spreading through online and offline activities;</p> <p>Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to adjust/update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.</p>
Scenario C	<p>Visualize a bar chart that shows the main trends linked to radicalization.</p> <p>Data coming from the social media will be used.</p> <p>The Policy Maker can select the keywords of his/her interest and consult the different information linked to them.</p>	<p>Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to adjust/update them or create new one based on the retrieved information.</p>

TABLE 1 – Scenarios Maggioli use case

2.1.4 Key Actors

The main actors involved in this Use Case are:

Role	Objective	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Policy Maker¹	Prevention, De-Radicalization, Reintegration		Analytical, Screening Techniques
Local authority / Municipality	Prevention, Reintegration	Community Engagement / Empowerment	Maintains informed about radicalization as a subject, Evidence based - healthy dose of skepticism
LEAs	Prevention	Training First Line Practitioners	Tempered and does not jump to conclusions

¹ Entities that may create and apply policies related to radicalization management. Includes public authorities at central level (e.g. regions, ministries, EU), which have different rights and enforcement capabilities. They are the end users of the PDT.

Role	Objective	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Policy Officers	Prevention		Ability to engage with people, Ability to build trust, Have empathy, Tempered and does not jump to conclusions, Effective initiator or partner in multi or inter-agency cooperation
Families	Reintegration	Educating Young People	Non-judgmental character
Teachers and educators	Prevention, Reintegration	Delivering Alternative Narratives	Willingness to spend time with young people, Ability to recognize/observe change, Intercultural understanding
Psychologist / school counselor	De-Radicalization, Reintegration	Family support	Ability to maintain relationship within a broad spectrum
Prison / Probation Practitioner	De-Radicalization,	Exit Strategy	Legal knowledge
Local community organizations and NGOs	Prevention, Reintegration	Community Engagement / Empowerment	Ability to engage with people and build relationship, Speak the language of minority groups, Intercultural sensitivities
Religious leaders	Prevention, Reintegration	Community Engagement / Empowerment	Ability to engage with people and build relationship, Speak the Language of minority groups
Journalists			Evidence based – healthy dose of skepticism

TABLE 2 – Key actors Maggioli use case

2.2 KPIs

2.2.1 Policy KPIs

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP1
Title	Reduction of time to develop a new policy to counter radicalization targeting vulnerable groups (e.g. children, youth, migrant)
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>50%

TABLE 3 – Maggioli policy KPI1

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP2
Title	Increase in community engagement and multi-agent cooperation in policy development
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>20%

TABLE 4 – Maggioli policy KPI2

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP3
Title	Reduce time to make prediction of possible risk of radicalization
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>25%

TABLE 5 – Maggioli policy KPI3

2.2.2 Technical KPIs

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP4
Title	Number of data sources integrated and linked to the PDT
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	>=3

TABLE 6 – Maggioli technical KPI4

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP5
Title	Number of open datasets about radicalization integrated in the PDT
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 2

TABLE 7 – Maggioli technical KPI5

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP6
Title	Increased number of algorithms / analytics tools used by the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	$> 20\%$

TABLE 8 – Maggioli technical KPI6

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP7
Title	New tools for visualisation of radicalization efforts integrated and used by the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 1

TABLE 9 – Maggioli technical KPI7

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP8
Title	Increased number of analytics tools (algorithms) used by the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	$> 20\%$

TABLE 10 – Maggioli technical KPI8

2.2.3 Business KPIs

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP9
Title	Number of identified occurrences of radicalization incidents in a given area
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 0

TABLE 11 – Maggioli business KPI9

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP10
Title	Number of identified active groups/individuals in a given area
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 0

TABLE 12 – Maggioli business KPI10

Section	Description
ID	MAG-KP11
Title	Number of new terms / keywords identified from the policy maker
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#1
Success Criteria	≥ 5

TABLE 13 – Maggioli business KPI11

2.3 Users Requirements

2.3.1 Visualizations Description and Requirements

For UC1 “Participatory policies against radicalization” the visualization functionalities are very valuable as they enable the policy maker to check at a glance the results of the selected data and thus understand what is happening in an area of his/her interest. Hence, the first type of visualisation option to be included in the PDT shall be the heatmap. An example is provided in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 – EXAMPLE OF HEATMAP FOR UC1

For this specific scenario, data will be retrieved from the GTD and RAND, which are already available in a structured format. The policy maker shall be able to filter the data based on different criteria (e.g., location, date, number of incidents, attack type, etc.). Thus, the system should show the different panels based on the selected criteria.

In the same way, the panels have to display the impact of terrorism for each criterion.

Number of terrorist attacks, 2017

FIGURE 2 – EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 3 – EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR UC1

Suicide attacks by target, male and female, Boko Haram, 2014–2018

Female suicide bombers were much more likely to attack public places.

FIGURE 4 – EXAMPLE OF PIE CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 5 – EXAMPLE OF STACKED AREA CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 6 – EXAMPLE OF LINE CHART FOR UC1

Distribution of deaths by terrorism, 1998–2018

Terrorism has remained widespread even as total deaths have declined.

FIGURE 7 – EXAMPLE OF BAR CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 8 – EXAMPLE OF CHART FOR UC1

The opinion of citizens could be collected from their concerns expressed in social media. The events that have had the most impact (number of likes, comments, retweets) could be showed in different panels, with the timeline, the date, source and link to the original document source.

FIGURE 9 – EXAMPLE OF LINE CHART FOR UC1

FIGURE 10 – EXAMPLE OF LINE CHART FOR UC1

Additionally, the most important terms could be displayed using tag clouds, used to check the frequency of texts, using different sizes (bigger with higher frequency) and colors:

FIGURE 11 – EXAMPLE OF TAG CLOUD FOR UC1

TOP POST

Four tweets are displayed in a list. Each tweet is contained within a light gray box with rounded corners. The tweets are as follows:

- Tweet 1:** "A ver si nos aclaramos: -La comida ecológica NO es más sana -NO hace falta tomar chía, lino, açafá o quinoa para comer sano -Comer sano NO es comprar pijadas en tiendas bio o macrobióticas -Comer verdura, fruta, legumbres o frutos secos Sí es sano. Da igual si son ecológicas o no" (18/10/2018)
- Tweet 2:** "-Sí hay alimentos malos, cuyos efectos nocivos están probados. Ejemplo: muchos de los que produce CocaCola, empresa para la que trabajaba este señor. -Ojalá el ministro haga lo posible por frenar el consumo de basura comestible, que tanto daño hace a la salud de los españoles. https://t.co/0fp9ABvUqo" (14/01/2020)
- Tweet 3:** "Si en tu confinamiento dominical no tienes muchas cosas en la nevera y quieres cocinar algo con ellas en lugar de pedir comida a domicilio, desde El Comidista podemos ayudarte: dinos de qué ingredientes dispones y te diremos qué puedes hacer con ellos. ¡Empezamos ya!" (15/03/2020)
- Tweet 4:** "¿Cómo avanzaron los negros con los derechos civiles, las mujeres con el sufragio universal o los obreros con las condiciones dignas en las fábricas? Calladitos en sus casas desde la "no polémica". https://t.co/KC8nxMvux4" (07/10/2018)

FIGURE 12 – EXAMPLE OF TOP POST OF TWITTER

In addition, it is also important to identify and take into account trends to predict possible risks and threats of radicalization. As an example, the Data Visualization Framework could display the information in the following way showing terms going up and down:

The dashboard, titled "Innovalimen", features a search bar and a filter section on the left. The main content is divided into four quadrants:

- ETIQUETA (Tags):** A list of tags with their respective counts, such as AZUCAR (62227), VERDURAS (51943), LECHE (50302), FRUTAS (47107), PASTA (24234), MAÍZ (20277), LISTERIOSIS (19889), ARROZ (19011), COVID19 (18863), TRIGO (18308), ACEITE DE OLIVA (17390), CEBADA (16616), CORDERO (15924), POLLO (14337), DIVULGADORES (13310), and CENTENO (10024).
- TEMAS QUE SUBEN (Topics that rise):** A list of terms with upward arrows and percentages, including "productos" (+3%), "conserva_vegetal" (+2.5%), "lacteos" (+2.3%), "covid_19" (+2%), "alerta_sanitaria" (+1.3%), "cerveza" (+1.1%), "refrescos" (0.8%), "café" (0.6%), "carnes" (0.5%), and "principales" (0.5%).
- CONCEPTOS QUE SUBEN (Concepts that rise):** A list of terms with upward arrows and percentages, including "harina" (+4.1%), "queso" (+3.1%), "manzana" (+1.9%), "huevo" (+1.6%), "cebada" (+1.4%), "yogur" (+1.4%), "cuarentena" (+1.3%), "guisante" (+1.3%), "alcachofa" (+1.3%), and "cordero" (+1.3%).
- TEMAS QUE BAJAN (Topics that fall):** A list of terms with downward arrows and percentages, including "planes_de_comunicación" (-3.5%), "edulcorantes" (-3%), "negocio" (-2.5%), "l_mas_d" (-2.4%), "comparteelsecreto" (-2.4%), "ingredientes" (-1.5%), "listeriosis" (-1.3%), and "vinos" (-1.2%).
- CONCEPTOS QUE BAJAN (Concepts that fall):** A list of terms with downward arrows and percentages, including "producto" (-6%), "integral" (-4.2%), "alimento" (-3.8%), "comparteelsecreto" (-3.8%), "edulcorante" (-3.4%), "azúcar" (-3.3%), "fruto" (-2.1%), and "listeriosis" (-1.6%).

FIGURE 13 – EXAMPLE OF UI DASHBOARD TO EVALUATE TRENDS

3 SARGA Use Case 2

3.1 Description

3.1.1 General Description

Use Case 2: Intelligent policies for the development of agrifood industry.

The agri-food industry in the Aragon region has annual sales exceeding € 2.5 billion, represents 8.8% of production and 11.86% of employment in the industrial sector in Aragon. Globalization and the increasing complexity of markets pose a threat to all traditional industries.

This industry is formed for the most part by small producers and SMEs with little access to new technologies, which is why it is important to collaborate with the Government of Aragon for the implementation of new investment methodologies in diffusion based on artificial intelligence. At this time from Aragon we want to give a boost to this important industrial sector, important not only economically but also socially, since we must take into account that this industrial activity takes place in rural environments, and for a region so punished by depopulation, the agri-food sector is the best tool to settle the population.

3.1.2 Main Objectives

- Improve investments in agri-food promotion by the Government of Aragon.
- Facilitate tools and access to new technologies for small and medium producers, tools based on open data, social media analysis, opinion mining.
- Improve the distribution of products thanks to the tool created in the project, a tool that allows them to search and compare prices and their positioning of their products and their rivals.
- Support for decision-making in the investment of the different geographical areas with market study elements based on artificial intelligence.
- Bringing the agri-food industry closer to new technologies.
- To support policy makers in the design and modelling of new policies / updating existing ones.
- Create stable working groups between producers and policy makers that allow to improve both communication and the development of new tools.

3.1.3 Use cases scenarios

Name	Description	Goals
Scenario A	Visualize the sale price of wine on the different specialized websites, with automatic warning systems that avoid penalties for contracts with large distributors.	Control of distribution prices of both its own products and those of the competition, allowing to improve commercial policy.
Scenario B	Visualize the negative and positive opinions on social networks of the different products analyzed allowing an automatic and immediate response to the end user.	Create an immediate communication with the end user, knowing their impressions, both positive and negative, that will allow us to interact with the end customer more directly.

Name	Description	Goals
Scenario C	Analysis of the trends in the wine sector through the specialized websites of the sector.	This action will allow us to know the trends in each of the markets that are of interest, knowing the trends in the sector we will be able to adjust our diffusion policies taking into account all possible parameters.

TABLE 14 – Scenarios Sarga use case

3.1.4 Key Actors

Actor	Role	Approach Sought	Skills and Competences
Policy Maker	Coordinate investment policies in diffusion of the wine sector.	Coordinate different administrations with competences in the sector.	Analytical, Management.
Wine producers (wineries)	Provide information on the needs of the sector and the development of the tool.	Collect information necessary for the project.	Specification of the needs of the sector. Analysis of the actions carried out so far.
Designation of Origin	Group producers information.	Meeting with small producers	Analytical Coordination
Regional promotion agencies (Aragón exterior; Sarga ...)	Coordinate promotional actions.	Coordination meetings to learn about the promotional actions carried out both nationally and internationally.	Marketing. IT experience.
Agri food cluster	Support in workshops and information analysis.	Coordination meeting.	Marketing.

TABLE 15 – Key actors Sarga use case

3.2 KPIs

Short description of the objectives of KPIs.

3.2.1 Policy KPIs

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP1
Title	Improve the impact of investment in agri-food promotion (wine sector)
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>20% sales

TABLE 16 – Sarga policy KPI1

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP2
Title	Coordinate actions of the different competent administrations
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>20% sales

TABLE 17 – Sarga policy KPI2

3.2.2 Technical KPIs

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP3
Title	Improve the flexibility of the data structure
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>20%

TABLE 18 – Sarga technical KPI3

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP4
Title	Provide real –time calculation capacity
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>20% of the data

TABLE 19 – Sarga technical KPI4

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP5
Title	Unification and or interoperability of data sources
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	10 data sources

TABLE 20 – Sarga technical KPI5

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP6
Title	Increase process speed
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>30% Reduce time

TABLE 21 – Sarga technical KPI6

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP7
Title	Increase speed of information access
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>25% Reduce time

TABLE 22 – Sarga technical KPI7

3.2.3 Business KPIs

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP8
Title	Increase efficiency. reduce time to make predictions of countries and target markets
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>50%

TABLE 23 – Sarga business KPI8

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP9
Title	Improve the success rate of new selected markets
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>30%

TABLE 24 – Sarga business KPI9

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP10
Title	Improve The economic performance of D.O
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>8%

TABLE 25 – Sarga business KPI10

Section	Description
ID	SAR-KP11
Title	Increases D.O. opportunities
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#2
Success Criteria	>15%

TABLE 26 – Sarga business KPI11

3.3 Users Requirements

3.3.1 Visualizations Description and Requirements

Images and text describing the visualizations shown on PDT. The objective is to think on most valuable and useful types of visualizations for each UC. For this, it is important a balance between valuable visualizations and the data provided, as data must provide all the information needed by visualizations in order to make them possible.

For the UC “Intelligent Policies for the development of denomination of origin” the visualization dashboards are very valuable as policies try to boost the promotion of the regional wine sector by providing support and aid for investment in wineries and by promoting wines in third countries; therefore these policies seek to ensure that the efforts and public resources invested are reflected in the wine market, one of the most competitive and specialized at international level.

FIGURE 14- EXAMPLE OF UI WITH USEFUL CHARTS AND PANELS FOR THE UC

For enabling policy makers to check in a glance the results of selected data analytics queries outcomes the following chart options with their associated data would be relevant for the use case. To collect the data and provide them from different perspectives, data sources can be filtered according to multiple criteria and show the different panels from several points of view. Thus, the data can be shown from several perspectives: distribution, competitors, customers, etc.

To identify the behaviour of the competitors and their strategies, both in sales and positioning, the data will come from the social networks probes that will be configured by indicating which competitors want to be considered and which will subsequently display the data under this competitive pursuit.

In the same way, the panels and dashboards have to display the impact of the campaigns on consumers. It may be useful to profile the type of consumer in order to try to determine whether demographic and social factors are relevant to the perception of wine and its consumption habits. For this purpose, radar charts could be very useful as shown in the example:

FIGURE 15- EXAMPLE OF CHART FOR CUSTOMER PROFILING

The opinion of customer could be collected from their opinions including panels and also the themes they mention. The documents of our customers that have had the most impact (number of likes, comments, retweets) could be showed in different document content panels, with the timeline, the date, source and link to the original document source. Additionally, the most important terms could be displayed using tag clouds, used to check the frequency of texts, using different sizes (bigger with higher frequency) and colors:

FIGURE 16- TAG CLOUD REGARDING THE WORLD OF WINE

FIGURE 17- EXAMPLE OF THE PANEL TOP POST

In addition, it is also important to identify and take into account trends in the wine sector to determine the topics and terms and its evolution by comparing time periods. As an example, the Data Visualization Framework could display the information in the following way showing terms going up and down:

FIGURE 18- EXAMPLE OF CHARTS TO EVALUATE TRENDS

To evaluate the efficiency in the investment of public funds for wine promotion and the study of new positions among new consumers, it can be exploited the data which comes from the influencers with the most representative users and those who have more followers, as well as the specialized websites to determine if the campaigns are well received by these users/media.

Moreover, the opinion of these users and media is extremely relevant, so sentiment panels are necessary to collect their opinions and analyze the sentiment reflected in their comments.

The following figure could illustrate as a general UI interface how to display opinion and sentiment:

FIGURE 19- EXAMPLE OF UI TO DISPLAY OPINION AND SENTIMENT

This chart could be used to display in a functional way which is the average opinion about a theme. It shows in a glance if the sentiment is mostly positive or negative:

FIGURE 20- EXAMPLE OF CHART TO DISPLAY OPINION MEDIA

This sentiment analysis could also be shown over the time using line charts. The example below can represent, for example, the behavior of opinion or sentiment about a topic over the time:

OPINION

FIGURE 21- CHARTS USED FOR SOCIAL MEDIA VISUALIZATION OVER TIME

And additionally, it can be shown the accumulative values using bar charts:

EMOCIONES DE FACEBOOK

FIGURE 22- BAR CHART TO ANALYZE SOCIAL MEDIA SENTIMENT

To analyze the data, different charts and visualization options are defined to better evaluate the data to be displayed.

4 SOFIA Use Case 3

4.1 Description

4.1.1 General Description

Use case 3 - Facilitating urban policy making and monitoring through crowdsourcing data analysis.

The aim of this use case is to support Sofia Municipality’s policy making in important areas of citizen’s areas of everyday life by using crowdsourced data via its Contact centre. By improving the policy making in these areas, the overall quality of citizen’s life will be improved, which is the overall goal of this project.

By using the powerful tools provided by PolicyCloud project, Sofia Municipality will be able to carry out a detailed analysis of the territorial distribution of the signals by categories / types, areas, districts, major transport roads, etc. The results of the analysis will allow the municipal and district administrations to identify the problems in the urban environment and to adopt or modify adequate policy making decisions on budget planning and effective use of budget and public resources. It will also help Sofia Municipality be focused on improving its policy making, related to better control and monitoring in these sectors, as well as preventing/avoiding risky or conflicting situations from happening.

4.1.2 Main Objectives

- To support policy makers in the design and modelling of new policies/updating existing ones by enhancing their knowledge and capability to identify, monitor and manage radicalisation efforts, in particular those targeting vulnerable groups (e.g. children, youth, migrants, etc).
- To improve the detection of potential risks of radicalization by early identifying warning signals and hidden patterns from heterogenous sources (including social media) using Big Data Analytics and machine learning techniques.
- To improve the community engagement and multi-agent cooperation on preventing and countering domestic radicalization leading to violent extremism.
- To evaluate the impact of (new) implemented policies/ countermeasures compared to the old ones.
- To share best practices and lessons learned with relevant stakeholders (at any level).

4.1.3 Use cases scenarios

Name	Description	Goals
SC1 - Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improve quality of service. - improve transport times and better connections for citizens. - assess multimodal pricing schemes and initiatives such as “Green ticket”. 	Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update/modify them or create new one based on the retrieved information.
SC2 - Parking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - adopt quantity measures for better parking management. - improve overall parking capabilities. 	Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update/modify them or create new one based on the retrieved information.

Name	Description	Goals
SC3 - Road infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- improving long term policy making in the area of road infrastructure.- better envisioning and capacity building of district administrations and municipal administration in solving road infrastructure problems.	Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update/modify them or create new one based on the retrieved information.
SC4 - Waste collection and waste disposal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- more efficient way of waste collection.- improvement of long-term planning and policy making of waste collection and waste disposal using smart meters.	Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update/modify them or create new one based on the retrieved information.
SC5- Air quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- improvement of long-term policy making in the area of air quality.	Validate existing policies and investigate if there is a need to update/modify them or create new one based on the retrieved information.

TABLE 27 – Scenarios Sofia use case

4.2 KPIs

Short description of the objectives of KPIs.

4.2.1 Policy KPIs

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KP1
Title	Increased efficiency: Reduction of time to develop a policy
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>50%

TABLE 28 – Sofia policy KPI1

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KP2
Title	Increase in stakeholders' engagement in policy development
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>20%

TABLE 29 – Sofia policy KPI2

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KP3
Title	Policy recommendations implemented in the annual city plan
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>25%

TABLE 30 – Sofia policy KPI3

4.2.2 Technical KPIs

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KP4
Title	Number of data sources integrated and linked to the PDT
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>=2
Section	Description

TABLE 31 – Sofia technical KPI4

Section	Description
ID	SOF-KP5
Title	Increased speed of access to information
Priority	High
Reference Use Case	UC#3
Success Criteria	>15%

TABLE 32 – Sofia technical KPI5

4.3 Users Requirements

4.3.1 Visualizations Description and Requirements

For Sofia use case Urban policy making through analysis of crowdsourced data, policy monitoring and analysis visualization tools have great importance. Analysing the data by category, type, territory and time will enable municipal and district administrations to identify problems, issues, and behavior trends. The analysis will also facilitate monitoring and control of the services under review, enabling preventative action to be taken where potential risk is identified, and guiding decision making around policy adjustment and/or adoption and also around the effective use of budget and public resources.

Visualization tools should support to obtain insights on effect of introducing or changing policies. They should allow for data analytics, which will enable the authorities to understand the effects of the change and find explanations for the behaviors observed.

To analyze the data, different charts and visualization options are defined to better evaluate the data to be displayed.

Visualization tools should be intuitive and at the same time informative. It is important that policy makers are able to efficiently assess data queries outcomes and impact, and to be able to connect deviation in results with alterations in inputs. Data should be able to be shown by various criteria, including cross analysis between different data sets.

Below images are exemplary, they do not contain relevant data and are non-exhaustive list of possible visualization options.

Example 1: Dashboards

FIGURE 23- DASHBOARDS SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.DECISIVEDATA.NET/](https://www.decisivedata.net/)

FIGURE 24- DASHBOARDS SOURCE: ESRI

FIGURE 25- DASHBOARDS SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.DECISIVEDATA.NET/](https://www.decisivedata.net/)

Example 2: Heatmaps

FIGURE 26- HEATMAPS

Example 3: Circular Area charts

FIGURE 27- CIRCULAR AREA CHARTS SOURCE: STACKOVERFLOW

Example 4: Tag Clouds

FIGURE 28- TAG CLOUDS SOURCE: BETTER EVALUATION

Example 5: Charts, bars, tables with dynamic criteria (by type, KPI, location, etc.)

FIGURE 29- CHARTS, BARS AND TABLES SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.DECISIVEDATA.NET/](https://www.decisivedata.net/)

5 LONDON Use Case 4

5.1 Description

5.1.1 General Description

This section of the document will be based on the use case scenario for work package 6: is to assist policy makers in creating effective policies that will address employment figures. The overall goal of this use case is for Policy makers to be able to use statistics from predictive algorithms from the toolkit to assist in making decision during policy creation process. The main objective will be to design the algorithms that will help predict future trends using the unemployment datasets provided.

5.1.2 Main Objectives

- Users should be able to use the platform to assist with the policy creation process.
- The PolicyCloud platform should produce visualizations that will be relevant during the
- Platform should be able to produce important KPIs.
- Visualizations that will highlight the correlations and information to help with decision making.

5.1.3 Use cases scenarios

Scenario A

Name	Goal	Activity
Conduct analysis based off the statistics on specific time periods. For example, the unemployment is expected to go up during the year 22 due to the current pandemic. Therefore the statistics recorded against the current year can help to identify the possible unemployment rate if there is second wave of infections the following year.	The goal of this scenario is to use the analytics and visualisations produced from the PolicyCLOUD platform to identify key information that could help determine groups of citizens that are affected by unemployment.	
Using predictive analysis to predict a future outcome.	The goal of this scenario is to use specially designed algorithms from PolicyCLOUD to predict future outcomes.	
Factors such as age, gender and time-based statistics such as month/ year will be key indicators to highlight common trends in specific age groups. Summaries of the total amount of unemployed citizens within a specific time period can be a key component to identifying significant trends.	The goal for this use case scenario is to identify trends in specific age groups. Once a particular trend has been identified then an appropriate policy can be designed based on what has been learnt from the data.	

TABLE 33 – Scenarios London use case

5.2 KPIs

Short description of the objectives of KPIs.

5.2.1 Policy KPIs

Section	Description
ID	LON-KP1
Title	Count of unemployed citizens under 25. This KPI will include a total count of all the citizens that are unemployed which are aged below 25.
Priority	N/A
Reference Use Case	UC#4
Success Criteria	Analytics based on the requested KPI should be clearly displayed in a number format or visualisation.

TABLE 34 – London policy KPI1

Section	Description
ID	LON-KP2
Title	Count of unemployed divided by age group. This KPI will include a total count of all the citizens and categorise them into various age ranges i.e. 25-40.
Priority	
Reference Use Case	UC#4
Success Criteria	Analytics based on the requested KPI should be clearly displayed in a number format or visualisation.

TABLE 35 – London policy KPI2

Section	Description
ID	LON-KP3
Title	A count of unemployed citizens divided by gender. This KPI will include a total count of all the citizens and categorise them by gender.
Priority	N/A
Reference Use Case	UC#4
Success Criteria	This field contains information on how to assess the fulfilment of this requirement.

TABLE 36 – London policy KPI3

5.2.2 Technical KPIs

Section	Description
ID	LON-KP4
Title	User Engagement. Numerical statistics that will track the number of users that engage with the platform
Priority	Potential log in system/ collect user's information via online form
Reference Use Case	UC#4
Success Criteria	Statistics based on the amount of user's engagement with the platform should be clearly displayed in a number format or visualisation.

TABLE 37 – London technical KPI4

Section	Description
ID	LON-KP5
Title	Log of errors. A feature within the PolicyCloud that tracks and logs and errors that users come across while using the platform.
Priority	
Reference Use Case	UC#4
Success Criteria	A system that logs all errors experienced by users with a id number and short description that define the details of the issue.

TABLE 38 – London technical KPI5

5.2.3 Business KPIs

Section	Description
ID	LON-KP6
Title	Feedback from optional survey. One of the
Priority	One question will have to specifically related to the user’s experience being negative or positive in order for the data to analysed and quantified.
Reference Use Case	UC#4
Success Criteria	Statistics based on the user’s experience with the platform can be produced and presented to stakeholders and reviewers.

TABLE 39 – London business KPI6

5.3 Users Requirements

5.3.1 Visualizations Description and Requirements

Images and text describing the visualizations shown on PDT. The objective is to think of the most valuable and useful types of visualizations for each use case. This aspect is very important a balance between valuable visualizations and the data provided, as data must provide all the information needed by visualizations in order to make them possible.

FIGURE 30- LINE GRAPH

Figure 30. Displays an example of the type of visualisations that would be produced to help in the policy creation process as you can see there is a clear yearly increase with the number of unemployed citizens on an annual basis therefore. This key information can trigger policy creator to investigate why citizens between 16 – 25 have a high rate of unemployment and what policies could be created to help that specific group of citizens.

6 Schedule

In the following timing we show the following developments and deadlines of the next deliverables related to WP6 Task 6.2 and the development of the use cases

SARGA

WP6 Use Cases Adaptation, Integration & Experimentation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
D6.10 : Use Case Scenarios Definition & Design M16 [16] (M16)	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■													
D6.11 : Use Case Scenarios Definition & Design M28 [28] (M28)																	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

7 Conclusion

This task collects information on fundamental aspects of the use cases and their development within the PolicyCLOUD project. Following a common methodology, the partners have identified the main actors, KPIs and scenarios common to the use cases of the Projects.

This deliverable is complementary to the previously mentioned ones where the requirements of each pilot case have been provided from a technical point of view.

As a further result of the works, there have been analysed and extracted the common features and functionalities between the pilots. This is a search for homogeneity in order to facilitate the specification of the tools.